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Leadership Style and Employee Achievement in Fast Food Firms in Anambra State

Ikelie, Izuchukwu Solomon & Dr. C.P Ohanyere

Department of Business Administration,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu, University, Igbariam Campus, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of leadership style on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State with the development of a leadership model. The specific objectives of the study were specifically to ascertain effect of charismatic leadership; to establish the effect of performance-focused leadership; to ascertain the effect of innovative leadership; to identify the effect of autocratic leadership, and to evaluate the effect of delegated leadership on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State. The study used survey research design to generate data from the respondents of firms under study through questionnaire. The study formulated five research questions and hypotheses respectively. The study was anchored on Path-Goal theory. Data were presented with descriptive statistical tables, frequencies and the analysis of the study were done with ordinary least square regression technique. The result findings showed that charismatic leadership, performance-focused, innovative, autocratic and delegated leadership have positive significant effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State during the period under study. The coefficient of determination (R^2) which determines the weight of the explanatory power of the predictor variables on the dependent variable and F-statistics for the model were 0.486 and 2.743 respectively. Charismatic leadership has a t-statistics of 5.533 and p-value of 0.002 which is statistically significant at 5% level of significance. Performance-focused leadership has a t-value of 3.509 with a probability value of 0.016 which is statistically significant at 5% level of significance. Innovative leadership recorded a t-value of 4.375 and a probability value of 0.02 which is within the acceptable threshold. Autocratic leadership recorded a t-value of 3.728 with an alpha value of 0.000 which is highly statistically significant. Delegated leadership recorded a t-value of 2.057 with an alpha value of 0.000 which is highly statistically significant. The study concluded that leadership style (charismatic, performance-focused, innovative, autocratic and delegated leadership) has a significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State. The study recommended among others that firms should engage a leadership style that gives employees a chance to express their creativity by coming up with suggestions to tackle a situation and charismatic leadership that allows for fair hearing as well and encourages equal participation. The study contributed to knowledge by establishing that leadership has significant positive effect with employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra state, Nigeria.

Keywords: Leadership Style, Employee Achievement, Fast Food Firms, Anambra State

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, organizations are operating in highly competitive environment. Effective leadership style is required for managing the organization successfully. The organizational success depends on its leadership styles and effectiveness of its employees. Mahmudi (2019) argues that employee performance is

influenced by various factors like leadership factors, personal/individual factors (knowledge, motivation and skills), team factors (cohesiveness and closeness of team members), and system factors (company culture). The leadership style adopted in an organization affect employee performance and have an impact on the success of achieving organizational goals. Most people know that person's leadership style can have an effect on organization's employee performance. In the food and beverage firms, the effect of leadership styles on employee performance, satisfaction, stress, and turnover intention has been thoroughly documented (Basit, Sebastian & Hassan, 2018). This study investigates the effect of leadership style and employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State. The effect of leadership styles on employee achievement is critical considering the developing concerns of the twenty-first century. Leadership has had a crucial effect in practically every facet of the society, according to Ricketts (Amegayibor, 2021).

Employee achievement is influenced significantly by leadership styles. This is because leadership is unable to cleanse itself of organizational failure. Strong leadership approaches make a big difference when it comes to overcoming challenges in the workplace (Amegayibor, 2021).The effectiveness of individual employee' achievement depends on the leader/supervisor. Effective leader can enhance the individual employee achievement through proper leadership style and retain high performance and talented employees within the company because he knows that high performance employees are unique resources of the organization. The ability to exert influence on some group of people toward some goals is leadership, and leadership is said to be pivotal to the success or failure of any organization, though there is no consensus as to what kind of leadership is needed to manned an organization but one common assertion is that leadership is the act of influencing some individuals toward common goals. The role every manager should fill in the workplace is leadership.

The behavior of leader is very important to improve job performance and retain skillful employees for longer period in the organization. According to the problems they face, leaders need to apply proper leadership styles. In some situations, employees leave the manager, not the organization. However, there are some other factors such as job satisfaction, flexible working environment, work life balance, work environment and career development opportunities. Leadership is the functional capacity to zealously push others to attain their maximum potential with integrity and responsibility, for both personal and professional advancement, by inspiring others via one's example (Soo, Tan, Tee& Yew 2022). Managers who seek the most excellent results should avoid relying on just one type of leadership. Onyebuenyi (2016), mentioned four factors influencing employee job satisfaction. They are as follows: organizational factors which includes salaried and wages, chances for promotion, and company policies; work environment factors that includes supervision, work group and conditions in the work environment; work itself that includes the scope of the job, variety, freedom and autonomy, role conflict and ambiguity and interesting work; and personal factors which includes age, tenure, and personality. There are lots of research disclosing the impact of the four main factors to employee job satisfaction. There are lot of study on employee engagement and performance but to the best of my knowledge, there is dearth on the effect of leadership style on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

When it comes to management, the link between an employee's situation and performance is weak and left to fend for itself. A lack of direction and strategic leadership in managing daily duties results in subpar employee performance. As a result, human resource management has gradually replaced personnel management to incorporate leadership styles into successful employee management or performance (Chua, Basit, & Hassan 2018). Leaders in the food and beverage business must recognise that, rather than architecture and facilities, human resources or employees play a critical role in assisting the firm in achieving its objectives. A company's success strongly depends on its employee performance. Thus, the firm should create environments that encourage and enable people to develop and enhance their skills and talents (Iskamto, et al., 2020). Leadership is vital to high performance since it organizes the company's human resource and fulfills corporate objectives efficiently and effectively (Udovita, 2020).

Excellent employee achievement will result in better and greater results for the company. Recruiting and retaining people who will be good leaders is one of the most pressing concerns in the food and beverages

industry. It entails holding oneself accountable and responsible for the entire group. It is all about maintaining consistency, momentum, and adaptability in a changing course (Roz, 2019). The leadership of the fast food industry determines its ability to function effectively. The power of persuasion over human resources, the source of competitive advantage for organisations, and the repercussions that follow are the pillars of leadership. Because having engaged employees is crucial for a company's performance, leaders must improve employee motivation to convince followers and harness employees' self-awareness of their professional commitments (Ebuzoeme, 2021). The fast food firms are a necessity for our human existence, and very little research has gone into this industry. This is also the purpose of our research, where we consider the ability of leadership to dominate other employee job achievement and its sensitivity to change (Gemedá & Lee, 2020).

Department of Statistics (2021) recorded a negative 1.7 percent in the volume index of service by the first quarter of 2021. This is because employees in this fast food service business were obliged to work overtime, long shifts, perform repetitive duties, and deal with difficult clients and poor leadership (Ghazali, Amran & Mohamad, 2020). In the fast food industry, fast food workers are virtually entirely automated, which lowers work motions and speeds up production, depleting employee skills to be depleted and makes work more difficult with equipment making decisions for them. As a result, over 38 percent of employees' working time is used on tasks that aren't related to the job requirements (Taşpınar & Türkmen, 2019). Additionally, according to the research by Akintoye (2017), managers struggle to motivate their fast food workers to work well because they lack effective leadership abilities. The fast food managers were not charismatic leaders who could inspire workers via their example which caused workers to react to these leaders in a routine manner and result in providing subpar performances (Banjoko, 2016). Thus, the fast food industry resulted in low job employee performance. It is possible to conclude that effective leadership can influence employees' performance, achievement and productivity levels in the fast food industry by referring to the facts above.

Since leadership is an integral factor in determining the success of an organization. It becomes significant that to attain corporate mission and vision as well as coping with the necessary changes occurring in the business world, leadership faces the burden of using the right leadership style. When a leader adopts the right leadership style following organisation culture, fulfillment of organizational aims and objectives is achieved (Roz, 2019). This study identifies the effect of charismatic, performance-focused, innovative, autocratic and delegated leadership on employee achievement in fast food industry in Anambra State Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

The fast-food industry in different towns in Anambra State Nigeria has been facing different challenges in improving employee achievement and satisfaction. In this modern world, the competition has increased. Most fast-food firms in Anambra State implement extra workloads without equitable pay on their employees and that make their lives hectic and miserable within the working environment. Retaining highly skill employees play a vital role in the industry in order to survive in the highly competitive world apparel market. The major problem of the fast food industry is in developing and maintaining the manpower required for its sustainability. Employees have a tendency to leave the industry after a short period of time largely due to long working hour, harsh working conditions and schedules, uncomfortable and low quality living arrangements. Higher employees' turnover can impact on the performance of organization. Lack of skilled labor and high labor turn over are one of the main challenges facing fast food industry in Anambra State Nigeria.

Furthermore, the ratio of forced labor has been increased due to the extra working hours and low wages provided to the employees. Bullying and threats in the Fast-food firms impact on effective leadership among employees due to the favouritism issues that arise in the fast-food firms. A company's ability to effectively manage, influence, and increase employee efficiency is required to achieve organizational goals. Employee achievement and satisfaction decrease if procedures are not followed correctly, especially when combined with an ineffective leadership style. The fast food industry in Anambra State Nigeria, where this research is centered, suffers from a lack of consistency in quality and low labor

efficiency, which is linked to the organization's leadership style. To boost staff productivity and employee performance, good leadership is essential. High employee achievement strongly depends on the leadership style. When a leader is using a suitable leadership style, he or she can influence employee's dedication, efficiency, and satisfaction. A major concern of leadership style should be demonstrated and considered by the leader to attain high job achievement among employees.

Therefore, leadership styles, employee achievement and performance have become an area of concern for this study. Hence, the study has chosen fast food firms in Anambra State Nigeria to observe this area. The present study focuses on the determinants of effect of leadership style in employee achievement by analyzing intervening effect of leadership model in fast food industry in Anambra State Nigeria. The goal of our study is to investigate the effect of charismatic, performance-focused, innovative, autocratic and delegated leadership on employee achievement in fast food industry in Anambra State Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

Leadership and Leadership Style

Leadership can be defined by the type of problem or situation being studied. Leadership is a term very active in human activity, so it is important to give a good definition of leadership (Silva, 2016). According to Hughes (2019), Leadership is the capacity to persuade people to work toward shared objectives. Next, a deep understanding of leadership makes it easier to influence others to accomplish goals. Leadership is found to be positively related to increasing employee performance and job satisfaction because leadership leads to efficient rewards and compensation and the provision of a good working environment for their workers. This eventually leads to enhance morale, motivation, and productivity of workers improving their performance and satisfaction with the job. Leadership style is the approach of a leader in providing directions, executing plans, and inspiring people. Many studies found that style of leadership affects the members of the team in many ways. Leadership can improve a person to show his abilities. Many companies need a person who has leadership skills, this is because the person can bring benefits to the companies. Leadership is a sought-after and valued commodity (Northouse, 2018). Furthermore, leadership can be defined by management. Management is more in control of the company to operational stability, then leadership is more in direction setting, change, movement, and persuasion. Next, leadership is needed to set a new strategy to solve the problem never seen before (Grint et al., 2016).

Leadership Style

This is the style in which a leader guides, motivates, and manages their team, and it is a product of their personal attributes, life experiences, philosophies, and attitudes (Smith & Johnson, 2023). Experts in leadership theories stress the critical importance of adjusting leadership styles to suit specific situations and contexts (Smith & Johnson, 2023). For instance, in scenarios where quick decision making is imperative and a leader holds more expertise than their team members, this approach involves making decisions unilaterally, often in high-pressure situations (Brown, 2023). Conversely, in situations when each member feels motivated and possesses similar level experience, a participative or innovative approach may be more advantageous. This style fosters collaboration and collective decision-making, thereby enhancing team involvement and satisfaction (Taylor, 2023). The effectiveness of a leadership style is a barometer of its success in achieving the team's objectives while simultaneously considering the well-being and interests of its members. Striking this delicate balance is crucial for sustainable organizational success (Md. Atikur, Rupali, Aman, Vikash& Md. Abdul 2023). A significant large corpus of research demonstrates the significant influence that leadership styles have on workers performance within organizations, underscoring their pivotal role in driving success (Md. Atikuret al., 2023). Charismatic leadership, a concept widely discussed in management literature, emphasizes the role of the leader in working collaboratively with their team to achieve significant changes. This approach involves inspiring and motivating team members towards a shared vision, often leading to profound organizational transformations. In contrast, the participative leadership style is centered on inclusivity in

decision-making. Leaders who employ this style actively seek and incorporate input from team members, fostering a sense of ownership and collaboration within the group (Davis, 2022). This is fundamentally different from autocratic leadership, where decision-making is centralized, and the leader's authority is paramount (Williams, & Davis 2023). Additionally, laissez-faire, and innovative leadership styles also play crucial roles in organizational dynamics. Laissez-faire leaders typically take a hands-off approach, allowing team members significant autonomy, while innovative leaders prioritize group consensus in decision making (Taylor & Brown, 2023). Richard Smith's analysis in 2010 highlighted these as the most pivotal leadership styles utilized across various companies, underscoring their importance in shaping organizational culture and effectiveness (Smith & Johnson, 2023). Each style has its situational advantages and can significantly impact employee morale, productivity, and overall organizational success.

Employee Achievement

Achievement is work performance, which is a comparison between work results and established standards (Retno, et al., 2020). According to the behavioral approach in management, employee achievement is a quantity or quality for something produced or services provided by someone who does the work (Luthans, 2017). Rivai and Basri (2019) stated that achievement is result or overall level of success on a person during a certain period in carrying out the task compared to various possibilities, such as work standards, targets or predetermined by criteria that have been agreed upon. Moreover, employee achievement was measured by six indicators such as quality, quantity, timeliness, effectiveness, independence, and work commitment (Swarup2020).

The performance of an organization is associated with the performance of a worker (Alan 2023). Employee performance refers to the job results both qualitative and quantitative that an individual or a group of individuals may do in line with their respective rights and duties in order to accomplish the goals of the firm (Kenny et al., 2020). Employee performance means how successfully the employees carry out the task assigned by their supervisors or managers. It describes people's capacity to accomplish tasks that influence the growth of a company's technological foundation (Santis et al., 2018). Employees' performance includes the timelessness of production, punctuality in the job, sympathetic and helpful character as well as their overall output in both quality and quantity (Widjajaa et al., 2020). Employee job performance generally depends on the employee's expertise, ability, competence, and actions that are generally required by the employees to accomplish their job (Pawirosumarto, Sarjana&Muchtar2017). Approaches to evaluate employee performance might concentrate on actions and job done instead of the worker's attitude (O' Brien, & O'Donnell2019). Through an organization's performance criteria, job performance is measured in terms of efficiency, effectiveness, productivity, work quality, and profitability. Efficiency refers to utilizing minimum resources but outcomes achieved are met with expectations while effectiveness refers to use capacity to attain desired objectives. A ratio of inputs and output has been used to calculate productivity (Putra et al., 2017). The capacity to produce money continuously over a set time period demonstrates profitability (Wood & Stangster, 2022).

Quantity refers to the total amount of jobs that have been produced in the specified time. Work time usage refers to the time estimated to accomplish the task or to manufacture products. Unfavorable situations such as delay, absenteeism as well as long working hours may help to indicate the low employee's performance. Cooperation with others in the office is defined as the capacity to work with other people to perform group work. Employee performance can be in-role performance and extra-role performance. In role performance enables workers in meeting the task objectives whereas extra-role performance enables workers to help other people in which they have acted over the expectations (Top et al., 2021). Work performance can categorise into task performance and contextual performance. Task performance was defined as the extent to what they carried out and finished assigned duties while contextual performance refers to non-core workplace behaviours such as work engagement, cooperation, and commitment for the organization's vision and objectives, which are all important inside the work. Thus, employee performance is vital as businesses seek profitability and success. Employee performance consequently

determines an organization's success, since bad performance limits a company's capacity to prosper (Pushpakumari, 2018).

Theoretical Framework

Behavioural Theory

According to the research conducted by Harrison (2018), the behavioral leadership theory emphasizes the way leaders assume and behave following the need of the employees and the workplace environment. Sometimes behavioral theory, known as the style theory, mainly suggests that leaders cannot be born but can effectively be developed depending on the learning behavior. The behavioral leadership theory emphasizes the potential actions of leaders as this theory majorly suggests that leadership success can be connected to the best predictor as it helps to view how leaders act in different activities. Actions instead of qualities have been recognized as the primary behavioral learning theory. The behavior patterns have been categorized and observed as the strong leadership styles in the behavioral theory. Few leadership styles comprised leadership with task-oriented quality, leadership with people-oriented qualities, and dictatorial leaders. Leaders' actual behavior and actions effectively describe the organization's success. The behavioral theory has several advantages. Initially, leaders can effectively decide and learn different actions they need to implement to create the leader kinds for developing vital job satisfaction criteria. It permits leaders to adapt and be flexible depending on several characteristics. Besides that, practical leadership styles suggest that every individual can become a strong leader. On the other hand, few behavioral theory critiques that it permits flexibility, as it directly suggests how to behave in specific circumstances. Several leadership styles relate to the behavioral theory. In fast food firms, leaders who exhibit supportive and directive behaviors can enhance employee achievement by providing clear guidance, feedback, and encouragement. Leaders should focus on developing their behavioral skills to create a positive work environment that fosters employee motivation and achievement.

Empirical Studies

Ndulue (2024) examined the effects of leadership style on employee's performance in United Nations Development Programme, Abuja, Nigeria. The following hypotheses were formulated in null form, they are Leadership style has no significant effect on employee's commitment to work in United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), Abuja. Leadership style has no significant effect on employees' productivity in United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), Abuja. Leadership style has no significant effect on employee's morale in United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), Abuja. The survey research design was used in the study. Data was collected from primary source with the use of questionnaire. The duration of study was between 2013 to 2022. Ordinary Least Square was adopted and findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between Leadership style and employee's performance in United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), Abuja.

Ndiritu, Ouma, & Okanda, (2024) established the influence of delegation on employee performance at four international airports in Kenya, namely: Jomo Kenyatta International Airport, Nairobi; Moi International Airport, Mombasa; Kisumu International Airport and Eldoret International Airport. Positivism philosophy was preferred in this study because it advocates for the use of accurate and verifiable evidence that is free from assumptions and opinions of the researcher. A survey research was used to conduct the study. The respondents were first line; middle level and senior level managers of the five departments involved in the processing of air passengers within the four international airports in Kenya. These were; airport security employees, port health and quarantine services employees, passenger airlines operating within the four international airports in Kenya employees, immigration and border control employees and finally the customs service's employees. Data was gathered from primary sources using self-administered structured questionnaires. The data analysis was done using descriptive and inferential statistics. From the Linear regression, the value of p was established as $p < .05$ (p value of 0.00 and $\beta = 0.474$) and therefore the null hypothesis was rejected indicating that delegation has a significant impact on employee performance

Abun, Valdez, Julian, Calipjo, and Macaspac, (2023) investigated how the innovative leadership of administrators, as well as the innovative knowledge and skills of employees impact their innovative work behavior. The study utilized a descriptive assessment and correlational research design, with data collected from employees at two colleges (DWCL & DWCV) using validated research questionnaires. Results showed that the innovative leadership of administrators, innovative knowledge, innovative skills, and innovative work behavior of employees were all assessed as high, and there was a significant correlation between them. These findings contribute to the discourse on innovative work behavior among employees.

Supriatna, &Zulganef (2023) investigated the Influence of Innovation Leadership on Employee Performance using motivating, influencing, and directing team members toward the intended objectives as specific variables. This study combines the two terms, reviews the innovative leadership style that discussed in the literature, and gives a general summary of how the two terms affect employee's performance. Result showed that the success of a company is greatly influenced by its leadership.

Chantal (2023) analyzed the relationship between leadership styles and employee performance. A variety of managerial positions, including democratic, autocratic, transformational, and many more, influence employee engagement and their overall contribution to the success of the company in different ways. A significant problem that triggered the investigation was the obvious decline in worker productivity within the company. The researcher came out with two main objectives that is to examine the kind of leadership styles practice in GloWiCC and to examine the effect the leadership style has on worker's productivity. In this study, questionnaires have been utilized to gather data. Participants were chosen through purposive sampling, encompassing a range of senior staff and essential operational personnel. The population includes some high ranking- employees as well as key operations workers and respondents selected through random sampling. The results showed that Global Wealth PLC mostly used an authoritarian leadership style, which has a big effect on worker efficiency. As a result, the study suggested that organizational leaders undergo thorough leadership training.

Nadia, Bahadur and Naimatullah (2023) investigated the impact of transactional leadership style (TLS) and entrepreneur's passion (ETP) for employee performance (EP) and mediating role of passion between TLS and EP in Pakistan. The study is a quantitative approach and based on cross-sectional data. In total, 356 cases are applied for the final analysis. The results demonstrated a positive and significant effect of TLS and ETP on EP. Thus, the ETP recognized as a mediator between the TLS and the EP. The study's findings would offer significant contributions and implications for executives, entrepreneurs, and managers. The leadership style perception of the employees has a considerable contribution to generating a higher level of job performance. Hence, the study would provide the smoothness in enhancing EP with leadership behaviours' development. However, the mediation investigation of ETP between TLS and EP among the employees of Pakistan would give further guidelines for the policymakers of developing nation to observe the role of ETP.

Muliyati, Lily, Wenny, Muhammad and Muhammad (2023) explored the literature in support of the variables in this scientific article and given results for consideration in future research as research gaps or with different research objects. The research method used is qualitative with literature reviews to get results. The results were obtained Most of the scientific articles of the review literature had a significant effect on the transactional leadership variable with employee performance, as well as the employee performance variable with organizational performance. Result showed that Transactional Leadership is significant with employee performance.

Sinurat, Sihombing, Sinaga, Gaol, and Sinurat, (2023) determined the influence of democratic leadership style, work status, compensation, and work environment on the performance of employees of the Secretariat of the Regional House of Representatives, Serdang Bedagai Regency. The research method used is quantitative data method, which functions to determine the focus of the study, select informants as data sources, assess data quality, analyze data, interpret data and draw conclusions from the findings. The results of this research with t test (partial) show that Democratic Leadership Style has no significant effect on Employee Performance. Working status has a significant effect to Employee Performance.

Compensation has no significant effect to Employee Performance. Work Environment has a significant effect to Employee Performance. The results of the f-stat (simultaneous) test show that Democratic Leadership Style, Employment status, Compensation and Work environment have a significant effect (simultaneously) on Employee Performance.

Chepkirui, Kitonga, and Pete, (2023) explored the transactional leadership styles and job satisfaction among the employees of the Multimedia University of Kenya (MMU) of Kenya. A descriptive survey research design was used. The study was guided by contingency leadership theory. Out of 386 employees of MMU, 197 supervised employees and 115 supervisor samples were drawn. Purposive sampling was used to select the study location and the study population, while stratified random sampling was used to select the individual respondents. Two sets of structured questionnaires were used to collect data. Data was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) version 26.0. The study found that supervised staff felt that their supervisors sometimes practised transactional leadership through contingent reward and management by exception. This study recommended that leaders identify individual uniqueness, link the individuals' current needs to the organization's needs, provide coaching, mentoring and growth opportunities, and implement a leadership that contains a mix of transactional and transformational leadership attributes.

Isgunandar, Ika and Risma (2022) determined the effect of democratic leadership style on the performance of employees in PD. Greater Makassar Parking. This research is a quantitative research that shows causation. The sample in this study were 51 people using the Simple Random Sampling technique and 3 informants. Data collection techniques used are questionnaires, interviews, and documentation. The data analysis technique used is descriptive data analysis and inferential statistical analysis. Based on the results of the product moment correlation test, the relationship between variables is moderate. Based on the results of simple linear regression analysis it was concluded that there is a positive and significant influence of democratic leadership style on employee performance. Choosing the right leadership style will have a good impact on the company. The results of this study state that the democratic leadership style tends to be open with employees, this can improve an employee's performance because they are able to work together and provide direct opinions with leaders. Based on the results of simple linear regression analysis it was concluded that there is a positive and significant influence of democratic leadership style on employee performance. Choosing the right leadership style will have a good impact on the company.

Gap in Knowledge

Empirical evidence had shown that various authors have undergone a study on the effect of leadership style and employee achievement in fast food Firms but very little attention is given to specific variables (charismatic, performance-focused, innovative, autocratic and delegated leadership) used in this study resulting to a variable gap. (Ndulue (2024; Chantal 2023; Mohammed & Rokshana 2023; Soo, et al., 2022; Santosh & Bimala 2022). The outcome of these studies showed mixed results on the effect of leadership style and employee performance. While some reported significant positive relationships between the dependent and independent variables, others reported negative significant relationship. Prabowo et al. (2018) found that charismatic leadership has no significance and has a negative effect on employee performance. For performance-focused leadership, studies found that this leadership style has a significant influence on employee performance (George & Hannah, 2020). But Kour, Sharma, & Andotra (2016) have proved that there is a negative effect of performance-focused leadership on employee performance. The findings of Joyce, Basif & Hassan (2018), showed that a democratic leadership style resulted in a positive and significant effect on employee job performance. Since there are mixed results of the five different leadership styles, which is significant, negative, and not significant.

However, as previously mentioned, most of the studies on the effect of leadership style and employee achievement have focused on the different firms in Nigeria resulting to geographical, methodological and subject content gaps. Thus, these are the gaps in our study. Therefore with the identified variables (charismatic, performance-focused, democratic, autocratic and Laissez-Faire leadership styles) this study, intends to fill both empirical and knowledge gaps to enhance the theoretical foundation of leadership style

and employee achievement in fast food Firms in Anambra State with the development of a leadership model.

METHODOLOGY

Research design

Descriptive survey research was adopted using questionnaire. Both primary and secondary data were used in this study. The study was carried out in Anambra State which is in South-East Nigeria.

Analysis Data

Analysis of the Regression results

Table 4.3.1 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.697 ^a	.486	.525	4.275	1.820

a. Predictors: (Constant), CHL, PFL, INL, AUL, DEL

b. Dependent Variable: EMPERF

Source: SPSS Version 21.0

Table 1 recorded R square value of 0.486 indicating that charismatic, performance-focused, innovative, autocratic and delegated leadership explain 48.6% of the variations in employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State. The Durbin-Watson statistics value of 1.820 in table 4.3.1 shows that the variables in the model are not auto correlated and are therefore, reliable for predications.

Table 2 ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	253.815	5	50.763	2.743	.018 ^a
Residual	6291.848	277	18.397		
Total	6545.664	282			

a. Predictors: (Constant), CHL, PFL, INL, AUL, DEL

b. Dependent Variable: EMPERF

Source: SPSS Version 21.0

The F-ratio in the ANOVA table tests whether the overall regression model is a good fit for the data. The f-statistics value of 2.743 with a probability value of 0.018 in table 2 indicates that the independent variable (charismatic, performance-focused, innovative, autocratic and delegated leadership) has significant positive effect on the dependent variable (employee achievement). This result indicates that charismatic, performance-focused, innovative, autocratic and delegated leadership can collectively account for the variations in employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State and therefore has goodness of fit for the data.

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	9.90	19.28	19.14	.855	282
Residual	-11.867	9.070	.000	4.258	282
Std. Predicted Value	-2.647	2.428	.000	1.000	282
Std. Residual	-2.767	2.115	.000	.993	282

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Achievement

The descriptive statistics in table 3 is used to describe the basic features of the data in the study. It provides simple summaries about the sample and the measures. Together with simple analysis, they form the basis of quantitative analysis of data. From table 4:3.3, the mean and standard deviation values of employee achievement during the period under review are 19.14 and 0.855 respectively. The statistics equally reveals that maximum number for employee achievement was 19.28 while the minimum was 9.90. However, the statistics showed that some of the sampled firms suffered negative minimum returns on their achievement during the period of study.

Test of Hypotheses

In this section, the four hypotheses earlier formulated in chapter one were testing using the t value and probability value in the regression coefficients outcome. The table is presented below:

Table 4. Coefficient of the Regression Result

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	24.004	3.816		7.505	.007
Charismatic leadership (CHL)	.124	.046	.155	5.533	.002
Performance-focused leadership (PFL)	.165	.067	.227	3.509	.016
Innovative leadership (INL)	.062	.078	.083	4.375	.002
Autocratic leadership (AUL)	.067	.085	.090	3.728	.000
Delegated leadership (DEL)	.224	.066	.235	2.057	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Achievement Source: SPSS Version 21.0

The unstandardized coefficients which indicate the variance of the dependent variable with independent variable when all other independent variables are held constant are indicated below.

$$\text{Empach} = 24.004 + 0.124\text{Charismatic leadership} + 0.165\text{performance-focused leadership} + 0.062\text{innovative leadership} + 0.067\text{ autocratic leadership} + 0.224\text{ delegated leadership}.$$

The coefficient for the intercept is 24.004 implies that if the predictor variables (charismatic, performance-focused, innovative, autocratic and delegated) leadership are equated to zero then the employee achievement will improve by a margin of 24.004. The beta coefficient of Charismatic leadership is 0.124 implying that a unit increase in Charismatic leadership will lead to an increase in employee achievement by a margin of 0.124. Secondly, the beta coefficient of performance-focused leadership is 0.165 meaning that a unit increase in performance-focused leadership leads to an increase in employee achievement by a margin of 0.165. Similarly, the beta coefficient of innovative leaderships 0.062 meaning that a unit increase in innovative leadership, leads to an increase in employee achievement by a margin of 0.062. Furthermore, the beta coefficient of autocratic leaderships 0.067 meaning that a unit increase in innovative leadership, leads to an increase in employee achievement by a margin of 0.067. Finally, a unit increase in idealized influence leads to an increase in employee achievement by a margin of 0.224 meaning that a unit increase in delegated leadership leads to an increase in employee achievement by a margin of 0.224.

Test of Hypothesis One

H0: Charismatic leadership does not have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

H1. Charismatic leadership have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

Table 4.4.1 indicates that charismatic leadership recorded a t-value of 5.533 with an alpha value of 0.002 which is statistically significant at 5% level of significance. Based on this, the null hypothesis is rejected

while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, charismatic leadership have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H0: Performance-focused leadership have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

H1: Performance-focused leadership have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

Performance-focused leadership has a t-value of 3.509 with a probability value of 0.016 which is statistically significant at 5% level of significance. Since threshold, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis. Hence, performance-focused leadership have significant positive effect on performance of SMEs in Anambra State.

Test of Hypothesis Three

H0: Innovative leadership does not have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

H1: Innovative leadership have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

Innovative leadership recorded a t-value of 4.375 and a probability value of 0.002 which is within the acceptable threshold. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis, hence innovative leadership have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

Test of Hypothesis Four

H0: Autocratic leadership does not have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

H1: Autocratic leadership have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

Autocratic leadership recorded a t-value of 3.728 with an alpha value of 0.000 which is highly statistically significant. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which states that autocratic leadership have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

Test of Hypothesis Five

H0: Delegated leadership does not have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State

H1: Delegated leadership have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State

Delegated leadership recorded a t-value of 2.057 with an alpha value of 0.000 which is highly statistically significant. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which states that delegated leadership have significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

CONCLUSION

The study examines leadership style and employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State. The data generated were analyzed using multiple regression analysis and the result shows that the explanatory variables of leadership style(charismatic, performance-focused, innovative, autocratic and delegated leadership) has a significant positive effect on employee achievement in fast food firms in Anambra State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

1. The study recommends that firms should engage a leadership style that gives employees a chance to express their creativity by coming up with suggestions to tackle a situation and charismatic leadership that allows for fair hearing as well and encourages equal participation. With this, employee's productivity would increase appropriately.

2. The study recommended that organizations targeting to improve organization performance must work on performance-focused company culture, degree of employee's inclination to be more productive, power of company financial incentives and team work. In addition, they must work towards discouraging delegation of tasks, career mentoring and coaching, and creation of new learning opportunities alongside a supportive climate.
3. The study also recommends that leaders should always encourage creativity and innovation in solving work related problems; always encourage critical thinking to issues before making decisions; always encourage new ways of solving problems and always encourage employees to appropriately re-examine critical assumptions to questions. When creativity and innovation is encouraged, employees will come up with new innovations that will take the enterprise a notch higher.
4. The study recommends that Supervisors should take risks to attain organizational goals through encouraging and emphasizing on employees learning and development. Supervisors should also talk about interpersonal relations, team cohesion as well as enabling decision-making at all levels of the organization, be sensitive to individual employees' needs, and take into consideration multiple alternatives when making decisions.
5. The study recommends that delegation to subordinates should not be seen as a favour as some top managers feel rather it encourages management by involvement (MBI) that builds capacity and enhances organizational excellence. Effective delegation needs to reflect the popular Pareto's Principle to ensure that organizational targets are achieved in an efficient manner.

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